

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS: A REVIEW**Neha Khaiwal¹ and Dr. Satyendra Gupta²**¹Research Scholar, School of Education, Galgotias University, Greater Noida, G.B. Nagar, UP.²Professor and Dean, School of Education, Galgotias University, Greater Noida, G.B. Nagar, UP.**ABSTRACT**

What affects the academic achievements of any student the most it's time management. Although most of the students constantly delay their academic work. This is what is called academic procrastination. Academic procrastination is a self-disabled behavior that affects people. There are many internal or external factors that influence students such as becoming distracted people who procrastinate are easily distracted by looking at an activity that is too interesting or fun. In the Academic procrastination, Procrastination Causes, Levels, Gender our search, on the other hand, was not constrained by a time limitation. This is a relatively typical occurrence that can lead to major performance and increased stress, students engage in academic procrastination when they put off completing tasks, projects, and assignments unnecessarily. Drawing on the literature- an attempt was made to identify the effect of academic procrastination on academic achievement. Academic procrastination is now a common phenomenon and its negative impact on student's achievement. When people try to complete their work in a rush until the last deadline, procrastinating can cause extra tension and anxiety. Academic procrastination and academic accomplishment were found to have a substantial association. At the end of this review, several suggestions for reducing academic procrastination are outlined.

Keywords: - Academic procrastination, Relationship, Academic achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Academic procrastination is a common problem which is found in all the people in some form or the other. This is especially a problem related to time management in students this problem is usually found, and they consider many factors responsible for it, such as the workload is so much that they are not able to complete it by trying hard. There are many such activities in the workplace which they find more interesting than that and they become more interested in doing it. Procrastination as a persistent failure to do what should be done to reach goals (Lay,1986). Academic procrastination has been coined to describe the overall tendency to postpone academic tasks in an academic setting. It is a common problem among students and many students must deal with it at practically every step of their education because of the negative effect which include academic failure and decreased well-being. Procrastination has recognized that people like to do those things which give them pleasure, they avoid doing what they do not like (Solomon & Roth Blum ,1984).

Academic procrastination is a self-disabled behavior that affects people. There are many internal or external factors that influence students such as becoming distracted people who procrastinate are easily distracted by looking at an activity that is too interesting or fun. Many social or personal factor are also responsible for procrastination. Time management skill also play a very important role in the work of procrastination because they should know which work should be given how much time or if they don't do it properly, they fail to manage the time.

There are certain things that symbolize people who procrastinate. Some of those are low self-esteem, self-efficacy, self-vital behavior, irrational worry of fulfillment or failure. A procrastinator is also said to be self-critical Because he has high expectations and wants to do something. But what will others say about him? This often does not allow such a person to begin. A procrastinator is someone who knows what he must do, even trying to do, but still doesn't (Poopla,2005). Similarly, the fear of success or failure is another characteristic of procrastinator. He is engrossed in the pain of success or failure before doing any work. That is why he is not able to complete any work even if he wants to. So, he keeps avoiding doing important work and wastes his time in other activities. Procrastinators lack self-esteem. He is late in doing any task because he believes that he lacks the ability to achieve any task sequentially. The destructive procrastination: - These are procrastinations according to the Ferron and Emmons (1994), who fail to pick up cues from the environment due to inability to defer gratification of pleasure, a lack of self-control, a lack of enthusiasm for accomplishing certain goals, and a lack of energy or organizational abilities. As a result, this sort of procrastination is frequently linked to a problem with time perception and estimation procrastinator who strives for perfection. This type of procrastinator prepares to work but refuses to do so, (Ellis and Knauss ,1977). This type of procrastination is thought to be caused by cognitive distortions or faulty thinking as a result, such procrastinators are hyper-aware and they are more likely to fear success or failure, which leads to neurotic avoidance. They lack self-efficacy and self-esteem, as well as being self-conscious and critical of themselves.

Definitions: - The Time period “procrastination” is product of parts “Pro” which means forward, beforehand and in aid of and “Crastinus” which means the following day as much as they are following day. This period derived from the Latin word “procrastinate” which means “swallowing”, “delaying”, “Pulling”, “Pausing”, “forestall moving” or “suspending a task”. This time period has been cited as a awful habit and behavioral trouble that’s skilled via way of means of many adults of their day by day works.

Causes: - crucial factor is that regardless of various definitions and thoughts concerning procrastination, motives of procrastination amongst personnel of the groups are nonetheless unknown, or even from time to time. Contradictory findings were executed on this relation. Time management is also one of the main reasons for procrastination. The procrastinator is found to have an inability to use time sequentially. He is not so goal oriented and keeps on wasting his time in low priority things. Due to this, he stops doing certain activities while focusing on non-productive activities. Another reason is that he is unable to concentrate due to external factors .as there are many distortions found in the atmosphere like; noise, teaching room is not appropriate, appropriate facilities are not available at home. Such students certainly do not take studies seriously and their only goal is to pass the class. That’s why let’s try to find the easiest way in the end and try to imitate others. Another main reason for procrastination is fear and anxiety. Instead of planning and completing them, this type of person is worried about what will happen in the upcoming tests and projects. There is another reason, refraining from doing these tasks is not the desire of the person to live or lack of knowledge and skills to do any work. Many times, the internal state of the person also becomes the reason of his delay.

OVERCOMING AND UNDERSTANDING OF PROCRASTINATION: -

- **Awareness:** - Firstly, to overcome procrastination you must understand the reasons why you procrastinate, and the work Procrastination acts in your life. You can’t come up with an effective solution if you don’t really understand the root of the Problem. So, reflect at the motives why you Procrastinate, your conduct and mind that cause procrastination.
- **Staying Motivated:** - if you are passive in class, you are probably not “entering” the curriculum and its subjects, and this undermines your motivation. Prevent that with the aid of using aiming to certainly recognize route material, now no longer memorize it or just get vid it. Instead, searching out what’s thrilling and applicable to you withinside the routl materials, placing your personal cause for each analyzing and sophistication session, and asking yourself (and others) question on what you are learning.
- **Be realistic:** - It takes time and effort to achieve goals and change habits; don’t sabotage yourself by having unrealistic expectations you can’t meet.
- **Self-talk:** - Pay attention to how you’re thinking and speaking to yourself. Talk to yourself in approaches that remind you of your desires and update old, counter-effective conduct of self-talk.
- **Time management:** To triumph over procrastination time control strategies and equipment are indispensable, however they are now no longer sufficient through themselves. And now no longer all techniques of handling time are similarly beneficial in coping with procrastination. There is a while control strategy which might be nicely desirable to overcoming procrastination and others which could make it worse. Those that lessen tension and worry and emphasize the pride and rewards of finishing duties paintings best.

ACADEMIC INTERVENTION FOR ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION

A review of the literature offers some examples of effective interventions for Academic Procrastination. One of the recent study the evaluation of the major characteristics and aspects of the procrastination (Balkis and Duru, 2007). The author state that common counselling and psychotherapy techniques have made some improvement with procrastination. However, specific behavioral and cognitive-behavioral techniques (such as systematic desensitization, relaxation training & rational emotional therapy) appear to be more effective in reducing procrastination. Structured intention setting, breaking down assignment and converting cognitive patterns inclusive of perfectionism and worry of failure or achievement are not unusual place middle techniques used to assist lessen student’s educational procrastination The author mentioned that behavioral and CBT strategies appear to be greater powerful than widespread counselling and psychotherapy. In a recent study getting up a flipped classroom design to reduce student Academic Procrastination (Gonda, D., 2021). In this research, he said that if we say that the child may be successful in flipped classroom, then it is very important to direct the student mind.

He holds two steps for the success of this research. First, the child should study with the written material, after that watch the video to understand the key points-second, along with watching the video, students can ask the

question to the teacher in the classroom. Due to this research, a change was felt in the behavior of the children and now they started doing mature discussion that if they flipped classroom design has the potential to enhance student's self-regulatory skills, which is reflected in a change in their attitudes towards learning responsibilities. Students' attitudes to online learning outside of the classroom have changed, and thus their chances of successful completing a combination course have increased statistically significantly are preparing for a classroom meeting. Research has additionally showed that academic procrastination may be decreased with the aid of using a flipped School room design.

Ones such studies (steel & Ferrari, 2013) Teacher intervention strategies observed withinside the literature is typically powerful and easy to implement. The do now no longer requite the direction teacher to have preceding understanding of an education in any unique remedy types. These interventions take region withinside the framework of the direction elected with the aid of using the pupil and do now no longer require attendance at conferences or participation in any specialized intervention programs. These teacher- primarily totally based intervention strategies are designed to goal all college students no matter bey and procrastination habits. This is a precious gain given the full-size incidence of procrastination amongst university college students.

Flipped classroom design has the potential to enhance student's self-regulatory skills, which is reflected in a change in their attitudes towards learning responsibilities. Student's attitudes to online learning outside of the classroom have changed, and thus their chances of successful completing a combination course have increased statistically significantly.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION

Academic procrastination is typically seen as a sign of a bad disposition. Murat Balkis (2013) stated his study that academic procrastination become negatively associated with rational ideals approximately analyzing, instructional existence. Pleasure and educational achievement. In contrast rational ideals approximately analyzing have been undoubtedly associated with instructional existence pleasure and academic achievement. The effect of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analyses confirmed that rational ideals approximately analyzing mediated relationships among academic procrastination, instructional existence pleasure and academic achievement. one of the other study on Analysis of procrastination among University Students. The researcher has taken 500 students in his study who are from Islamia university. He focused on his study which analyzes the factors of procrastination and its impact on the learning of university students. He divided his study into 5 parts-areas of procrastination, reason of procrastination, effect of procrastination on learning of university students, negative social effect of procrastination, remedial measures. And he found the effect of procrastination on learning of university students that Academic procrastination has a negative impact on student's studies resulting in their low achievement in examinations, or it causes failure in examinations, or it creates fear of examination resulting in depression and anxiety, lowering their morale. They feel hesitant to start their academic work losing their competitive spirit students become victims of inferiority complex and eventually stop their studies. (Akinsola, Adedeji Tella, Adeyinka Tella ,2007). Correlates of academic procrastination and mathematics achievement of Undergraduate students reported that Academic procrastination achievement is causing more harm to the students, it is having a negative effect on their studies. A total of 100 part 3 and 4 students from the department of mathematics and mathematics education at the Universities of Lbadan and Lages, Nigeria was used in the study. (Tuckman ,1991) designed and validated a 35- item academic procrastination scale, which was used to collect data, along with the subjects GPA score to date in mathematics and the study results also indicated that there is significant difference between Procrastination and math achievement, with a student with low procrastination having higher achievement in math than students with moderate and high levels of procrastination. This has very important implications for the quality and number of students who become available for higher studies in the field of mathematics in his study. Scholar said about the gender difference that Academic procrastination and Gender difference are independent of Each other. This means that both males and females procrastinate in Similar manners. Tuckman (1991) emphasizes that Procrastination describes themselves as people who doubt their abilities and that each gender entity has its share of such people. (Bashir and Gupta ,2018) A deeper look into the relationship between Academic Procrastination and Academic performance among universities students stated that academic Procrastination is now a common phenomenon which adversely affect the student's performance. They used convenient sampling and conducted their research on 380 university students. He found in his study that a significant negative association exists between academic procrastination and the academic performance of university students. The academic performance of pupils was also severely impacted by aspects of academic procrastination such time management, work aversion, conscientiousness and personally initiative. According to the findings, people who

experience significant intellectual delays perform poorly in School. (Kim & Seo, 2015) They conducted a meta-analysis of the relationship between procrastination and academic performance and stated that academic performance was negatively correlated with academic Procrastination. They gathered these results using a meta-analysis of 33 pertinent studies with a total of 38,529 participants. The results of this analysis showed that procrastination was negatively connected with academic success, the choice of measurements or indicators had an impact on this connection. The detection of a substantial link between procrastination and academic achievement was hindered using self- reported scales. The observed association was also impacted by the participant’s demographic makeup in each study.

In conclusion, we can say that there is negative relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement. Academic procrastination act as a negative variable on the students and behave in a manner that leads them to laziness and anxiety. On the basis of all these reviews we check our study by dividing it into demographic variables.

- a) On the basis of gender
- b) On the basis of levels

Figure No. 1

GENDER

Hakan Karatas (2015) in his study Correlation among academic procrastination, personality traits and academic achievement state that the correlation among Academic procrastination, personality traits and academic achievement. Researchers find the negative relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement. The impact of personality qualities, particularly the conscientious dimension, an academic procrastination and accomplishment is demonstrated in the study. First and foremost, it is critical to remove the barriers that cause procrastination, which has a detrimental impact on student’s learning, resulting in bad grades or failure in exams, as well as despair and anxiety during the school years. Academic advisors, counsellor, and educators should be particularly interested in this result. New academic programmes are being developed to assist students in overcoming academic procrastination, which is one of the leading causes of poor academic performance. The researcher in this study also finds that the role of gender differences in academic procrastination and said that role of gender in academic achievement, which is in favor of girl students. The literature cites these results as female students using self-regulation strategies more frequently and effectively. Murat Balkis &Erdin Duru (2017) The study was designed to examine the gender differences in the relationship between academic procrastination, academic performance, and satisfaction with academic life. Researcher used in his study 441 under-graduate students (49.4% of female and 50.6% of male) and finds that academic procrastination was inversely associated with academic performance and satisfaction with academic life. Female student reported lower level of academic procrastination that male counter parts, and higher levels of academic performance and satisfaction with academic life. These findings suggested that male students were more prone to procrastination, receiving low grades and being dissatisfied with academic life, male students should be the focus of an intervention programme developed by a college psychologist and counsellor. A psychoeducational

course tailored to boys could be offered to assist them develop coping techniques for their dilatory conduct. Examining the differences in procrastination Tendencies among university students Mandap, M.C. (2016): Gender disparities in procrastination were discovered, with male students procrastinating more than female students. Because of their hatred of activities and the perceived difficulty of completing a task, male students had greater procrastination scores. Procrastination scores were substantially greater among students with low perceived academic self-efficacy than in students with strong self-efficacy when students were divided into group based on the sort of academic course they were taking and their degree of achievement, no significant differences in procrastination scores were detected. Jabeen Khan (2014): Academic procrastination among male and female university and college students. He took a sample of 200 students in his study. He did his study with 3 objectives. Examine the gender differences in academic procrastination, to investigate the variations in procrastination across college and university students, to research academic procrastination across age groups. He found in the result that Male students will have more delays than female students. The results show that male students procrastinate more than female students, procrastination behavior among college students will be higher compared to the university. The result of the present study demonstrates a significant difference between the two groups. Delays will be more in students below 20 years than those above 20 years of age. Taking age factor into academic procrastination reveals age factor into academic procrastination reveals significant difference between age groups. Younger individuals procrastinate more than older persons.

Based on all reviews, we can say that low level of procrastination is found in girl as compared to boys.

LEVEL

To examine the relationship between academic Procrastination and academic achievement we divide our study into levels. A review of literature offers some examples of levels.

A cross sectional study on Procrastination: Who procrastinate more?

(Ozer, U., 2011) Examined the level and prevalence of academic procrastination on high school, undergraduate and graduate students. According to the findings of the descriptive statistics conducted on each group, undergraduate exhibit the highest level of procrastination. The high school participants procrastinate less than the other two student's groups, according to the result, and graduates are the second category of procrastinators. He also examined that student in high school and college admitted to procrastinating on studying for examinations almost always or always. Whereas graduate students allegedly procrastinate more when it comes to completing terms papers. One of the recent studies on academic procrastination: prevalence among high school and undergraduate students and relationship to academic achievement (Jill Jansen, 2015) stated that: -For teachers, counsellors, and parents these discoveries how significant, educational ramifications. He examined that we can better understand how academic procrastination manifests itself as a student's age by comparing the prevalence of procrastination and undergraduate college students. He also suggested people who struggle with procrastination may need to start with the simplest task and work their way up to more difficult and demanding activities. Students are more inclined to put off finishing larger projects.

Not much research has been done in this field yet, but we can say on the basis of their review that graduate students procrastinate more than higher school students, age factor has a dual role e.g., 20-25-year-old students more procrastinate. Because at this age size, they prefer to spend most of their time in their peers group and like to do the same work or activities that their peer group is doing, which has negative academic impact on them.

DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTIONS

One of the most crucial elements of the educational system and the main determinant of how well a school is doing is the academic achievement of the student's Academic success is influenced by both internal and external influence, with academic procrastination being one of the internal and external influences, with academic procrastination being one of the internal causes. Therefore, the goal of the current study was to draw conclusions on the relationship between demographic variables academic procrastination and performance, while it is obvious that academic procrastination is a serious issue that must be handled on a personal and environmental level, procrastination exhibit trails like a preference for easy schoolwork, poor time management, a referral to explain their skills, difficulties making decisions and a tendency to dwell on the past. As a result, they waste chances, abandon jobs unfinished and put off doing work. The study examined academic intervention for academic procrastination as well as the association between academic procrastination is associated with poor academic achievement, according to the systematic research. Low achievement could be an unavoidable side effect of procrastinating. According to our findings, (Kim, S. & Lee, 2015) also investigated the possibility that academic procrastination and academic accomplishment have a bad relationship. This study found that pupils with low academic procrastination outperform those with high levels in terms of academic

accomplishment. Our findings also supported by Murat Balkis & Erdin Duru (2017) that female students reported lower level of academic procrastination in comparison to male students. According to review we can say that undergraduate students show maximum procrastination among high school and graduate students. Based on reviewing many papers, academic procrastination can be cure with the help of intervention program and the study has given suggestions to the teachers as to how he can save the students from procrastination.

Figure NO. 2

IMPLICATIONS: -

The study findings show potential practical applications. It is important to remember that procrastination has detrimental effect on student's lives, and many students have run into difficulties because of their attitudes and practices toward procrastination. Researchers need to come up with useful strategies to assist students in lessening the frequency of this activity since many students have been discovered to be aware of it and have stated that they desire to do so during tests, when doing assignments and when writing term papers. It is recommended that some programmes be developed and implemented to instruct pupils in task oriented coping techniques.

CONCLUSION

The study was divided into two parts, one based on gender, and one based on level. Reviewing many literatures found negative associations between academic procrastination and academic achievement. When studying based on level and gender, undergraduate students is more procrastinate than high school and graduate students, male is more procrastinate than female.

The association between academic procrastination and academic accomplishments is the main topic of this study. The findings of this preliminary research demonstrate that there is a significant link between these variables. Academic procrastination, however, can also be regarded as the failure to complete an academic task within the anticipated or desired time range despite knowing that one must and possibly wishes to do so.

SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER RESEARCH: -

No research is Complete in itself. Due to limited time and resources, the researcher limited the research as it was not possible to deal with all aspects of the problem under consideration. Therefore, some suggestions for further research based on present study experiences are given below: -

The present study has been conducted by using only one variable academic procrastination. Similar study can variables like: - Anxiety, stress, self-efficacy, Motivation level etc.

The present study was delimited to Gender and level.

Further it can be extended to another level. i.e., 0Age group, School type (Government and private). Etc.

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